

Synthesis of findings on the impact of institutional frameworks from the set of 15 case studies

MATS Deliverable 4.1

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Summary

This report looks at the impact of institutional frameworks in the 15 case studies (CS) and aims at synthesizing the related learnings therefrom.

The CS reports show variety in terms of completeness and detail of analysis on legal and institutional matters, also a reflection of the planned ongoing CS work and the differences in CS focus with respect to analysis methods and empirical settings. To a variable degree, CS reports focus on international trade, domestic law, supply chain organization, competition, food production, investment and social as well as environmental sustainability questions. In other words, the CS reports vary in terms of in-depth consideration of legal, governance and institutional aspects.

Furthermore, several areas of law such as international environmental law and human rights law have received limited coverage in the CS. Also, other areas of law related to Intellectual Property (IP) are receiving little attention, in particular with respect to patents, trademarks, copyrights, and geographical indications. This is remarkable since such areas of law are related to competition and innovation issues and may be especially relevant in the agricultural trade and sustainability nexus in the future, considering also the forthcoming transition pathways analysis (WP5).

The report provides an initial synthesis of general findings and then a dedicated focus for every CS, based on information that is currently available.

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Synthesis of findings on the impact of institutional frameworks from the set of 15 case studies

Introduction

According to the terms of reference for WP4, the Maastricht University members of MATS are responsible for analyzing the case studies in light of a set of fields of law, including trade law, food law, and intellectual property law, amongst others, and provide a synthesis of findings. We relied on information currently available for each CS. Based on this information, this report delivers initial, general and CS-specific findings.

General Findings

Based on our initial assessment, we reached the following five general findings:

First, the CS reports vary widely in terms of progress. While some CSs have produced detailed conclusions and recommendations (e.g., CSs 8, 10 and 13), others have set out their objectives, or are still in further data analysis phase (e.g., CSs 2, 7), and one report is still missing due to ongoing fieldwork (CS 11). This diversity in progress is thus also a reflection of the long CS implementation phase as per Grant Agreement (GA).

Second, and relatedly, the CS reports vary in terms of in-depth consideration of legal and institutional aspects. In spite of the fact that CS leaders were made aware of the potential relevance of legal and institutional aspects in their particular context (D3.1 *Methodological guidelines and reporting template*), the CS reports document different levels in terms of the coverage, general understanding and awareness of the applicable law and the impacts of the institutional dimension, mostly in terms of the powers of different regulatory authorities. Therefore, reporting depth on each CS (see next Section) will vary substantially.

Third, the CS reports focus on certain areas of law, with, so far, limited consideration of other areas of law that might potentially be relevant too. It is important to note that the case study reports raise other legal issues not specifically covered in the fields analyzed here, such as (international) labour law, land rights, indigenous rights, and environmental law. Taking those other areas of law on board could contribute to a deeper understanding of the relevant legal issues for each CS and enrich the ongoing WP5 – *Transition pathways and policy recommendations* - work.

Thus far, the reports focused much on international trade, supply chain organization, food production, and sustainability questions, in terms of both private and public rules. Specific areas of law like IP (especially for patent, trademark, copyright, and geographical indications) and competition are barely addressed, which is also a reflection of the perceived relevance of these issues by CS actors, relative to other issues deemed relevant at individual CS level by the same CS actors. For example, in cases from 7 to 15, there is a lack of coverage of intellectual property and competition law questions. Considering the potential relevance of these questions also with respect to WP5 transition pathway analysis, there seems to be space for incorporating considerations or discussing these issues further with stakeholders (WP5, WP6). In addition to that, some CSs have a product-specific value chain approach, while others look at the legal framework more broadly, explaining further the observed diversity in the consideration of areas of law.

Fourth, generally speaking, the CS reports focus on the institutional framework, and the role of different actors in the supply chain. What emerges from the different analyses, is specific attention to the institutional framework, or, in other words, not only to the legal sources but also to the actors that play an important role in determining the rules for the specific supply chain. There are many references related to possible areas of cooperation among different bodies, the risk of fragmentation, reflections on the architecture of producer associations, and a general call for more transparency.

Fifth, and finally, some CSs give recommendations for changing the legal frameworks that affect their supply chain. For example, CSs 1 and 4 provided a much more detailed list of recommendations based on specific as-

assumptions but generally applicable to other CSs. They highlight the importance of applying risk-based principles to regulation, to streamline bureaucracy and procedures, and to revise old, redundant, and inefficient legislation. Some challenges are of common concern: *e.g.*, how to regulate informal markets for certain areas, a too-narrow legal basis that does not address sufficient sustainability or human rights issues, and a call for more harmonization and cooperation.

Case Study #1

Ability to reduce poverty of smallholder farmers through trade and value chains for coffee in Uganda and Tanzania

Lead organization & name of lead contact: University of Helsinki, John Sumelius

Introduction

This case study, which is being conducted in Tanzania and Uganda, aims to evaluate the effects of certain trade regimes, practices, and laws at the local, national, and international levels as well as how these trade regimes and practices help smallholder farmers become less impoverished. The case study makes a comparative analysis of how the organization of the coffee value chain and the position of smallholders differs in the two countries.

References to the different legal fields

The report puts emphasis on how coffee is a product that is affected by both domestic government measures and export requirements. In relation to Tanzania, the study has a very comprehensive perspective on the relevant legal sources. It looks at the domestic level (also in terms of regulatory actors), there are few references to local requirements, and the EU legislation is addressed as well as the international one, mostly for free trade agreements (FTAs). Private standards (like Rainforest Alliance) are discussed and there is specific attention to human rights concerns. In Tanzania only, legal requirements analyzed concern both the food safety and the food sustainability area. The study combines a wide perspective on trade issues together with specific and technical requirements for the coffee value chain. In this sense, there is both a general (horizontal) and a product-specific (vertical) understanding of the relevant legal issues.

Assessment of the relevant legal provisions

The assessment of the relevant legal texts involved and directly related to issues addressed in the case study will be presented in the final version of this commentary. Legal reflections for Uganda are missing at this stage.

Case Study #2

Intra-EU trade, resilience and social sustainability: the case of the oats value chain in the Nordics

Lead organization & name of lead contact: University of Helsinki, Bodo Steiner

Introduction

The purpose of this case study is to evaluate the social sustainability measures that are addressed in the Nordic oat value chains of Sweden and Finland, as well as the potential relevance of these measures—and their omissions—for the sustainability of intra-EU trade in oats and oat products as well as the resilience of these value chains.

References to the different legal fields

While it is indicated that a focus is placed on key governance / legal/ institutional / trade policy frameworks that play a role in relation to mechanisms for pricing transparency and price data sharing and implicit or explicit sustainability standards/requirements, the report does not actually address specific legal issues.

Assessment of the relevant legal provisions

There is no assessment of the relevant legal texts involved, as the secondary data analysis of this CS deemed other issues more relevant. Once the final data analysis has been reported, relevant legal issues directly related to the case study will be presented in the final version of this commentary, taking also all information from the case study summary report (D3.5.) into account.

Case Study #3

Trade, sustainability and environmental linkages in Finnish dairy production

Lead organization & name of lead contact: University of Helsinki, Nina Hyytiä

Introduction

The environmental, climatic, and economic aspects of the dairy trade are the main topics of this case study. In case study 3, the environmental and climatic effects of the regional dairy industry in Finland are measured, and the possible effects of pricing strategies for these effects are approximated.

References to the different legal fields

The primary focus of the study is devoted to the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), and more specifically, the recent replacement of previous CAP programs cross compliance and greening with conditionality. Significantly, the new Conditionality system allows for more member state autonomy, and the Finnish situation is considered with these preliminary remarks. Agricultural Law is only one part of the relevant frameworks addressed. Detailed references are made to the so-called Animal Health Law. The perspective on national law is closed by highlighting rules on milk product safety and quality. There are closing legal references to the international dimension, namely the WTO (SPS Agreement) and some FTAs signed by the EU particularly important for the dairy sector.

Assessment of the relevant legal provisions

The assessment of the relevant legal texts involved and directly related to issues addressed in the case study will be presented in the final version of this commentary, taking also all information from the case study summary report (D3.5.) into account.

Case Study #4

Enhancing Access to Export Markets by Sub Saharan African (SSA) Countries through Sustainable Investments to Ensure Quality of Agri-food Commodities: The cases of Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana

Lead organization & name of lead contact: The Economic and Social Research Foundation (ESRF), Tanzania. Dr Hoseana Bohela Lunogelo, Dr Daniel Ngowi, and Prof Deus Rwehumbiza

Introduction

This study falls under the themes of market access and sustainable investments in producing surplus high-quality agri-food commodities for the export markets. The four countries that were selected to represent typical agricultural sector-dependent countries in the four main economic blocs under the African Union. The study aims to answer two different questions. First, how the trade policies of the corresponding nation, foreign and local investments flowing into the agri-food value chains, and the sustainability criteria that were implemented have affected the socioeconomic and environmental situations on a local, national, and global scale. The second issue addressed is how governments may promote the beneficial effects of agri-food commerce and trade policy regimes on sustainable development and human rights while mitigating their negative effects with assistance from the international community.

References to the different legal fields

In relation to the case of Tanzania and the roots, tubers, and cassava markets, there are no dedicated references to the legal field. For the focus on Uganda and the banana supply chain, there are detailed references to the legal and regulatory frameworks for exports. The report claims that Uganda's trade related legal and regulatory framework is robust and conducive for all forms of investment, including in organic agriculture. The report also provides pertinent legal reform recommendations. The case of goat meat in Ethiopia is also rich of references and reflections, and focused on the necessity for

producers to meet EU and other international markets requirements. Also the domestic level is considered, with the few relevant national legislation. In the end, the Ghana cocoa sector is considered as a matter of policies, laws (national), and institutions.

Assessment of the relevant legal provisions

The assessment of the relevant legal texts involved and directly related to issues addressed in the case study will be presented in the final version of this commentary, taking also all information from the case study summary report (D3.5.) into account.

Case Study #5

Role of policy frameworks and social cohesion for sustainable value chains and livelihoods in Ghana

Lead organization & name of lead contact: Technical University of Madrid, Pablo Vidueira

Introduction

The primary objective of the study is to ascertain how improved governance mechanisms and policy frameworks enhance the competitiveness and sustainability of domestic poultry meat and protein self-sufficiency at the national level and provide respectable living conditions for farmers and other poultry value chain actors.

References to the different legal fields

The report stresses how, in order to develop Ghana's domestic poultry market, social cohesiveness and policy frameworks are crucial. The emphasis is on a policy framework that should be able to: (i) make it easier for chicken farmers to access high-quality inputs and facilities; (ii) encourage the development and uptake of practices and technologies that support sustainable poultry farming; and (iii) safeguard and promote the production and consumption of domestic goods. Together with the policy framework dimension, the report looks at the contribution that credit unions, farmers' groups, and other forms of social cohesiveness provide to the advancement of the chicken value chain. In addition to that, relevance is also given to public authorities, namely, the government, research and development organizations, and financial institutions. The whole report looks more into the possible positive impacts of a revised legal and policy framework than the current situation. The institutional dimension is addressed in a similar narrative, identifying all actors that may contribute to the improvement of the poultry meat sector.

Assessment of the relevant legal provisions

The assessment of the relevant legal texts involved and directly related to issues addressed in the case study will be presented in the final version of this commentary, taking also all information from the case study summary report

(D3.5.) into account. At the moment, in the report, the literature review is yet to be completed.

Case Study #6

Analysis of cocoa and chocolate purchasing practices that could undermine living incomes for cocoa farmers (West-Africa – Belgium)

Lead organization & name of lead contact: Oxfam Wereldwinkels, Bart Van Besien

Introduction

The study looks at debates and negotiations around the introduction of the living income differential for the cocoa sector in West-Africa, as a measure different, and with a limited impact, from the living income floor price. The general purpose is to better comprehend the decisions made by institutional or private players that result in low farm gate pricing and farmer poverty, which are strongly at odds with the above negotiations. The study finally aims at finding the linkages between different actors in the cocoa sector and identifying where power really lies.

References to the different legal fields

The report tries to link the research with the ongoing policy agenda. In particular, it highlights the global trend which sees an increased interest in disclosure and transparency in the law, as well as the introduction of mandatory human rights and environmental due diligence measures. Examples are made at the national (France, Germany, etc.) and EU level. The initiative of private parties (companies) is also acknowledged. There are open issues about the role of legal frameworks and their developments in order to guarantee the protection of the rights of farmers and workers through human rights practices. Multi-Stakeholder-Initiatives are also invoked as actions that may contribute to sustainability in the cocoa sector. At the general level, there is specific attention to the role of different actors, like private companies and local public authorities, like the Ghanaian Public Cocoa Board.

Assessment of the relevant legal provisions

The assessment of the relevant legal texts involved and directly related to issues addressed in the case study will be presented in the final version of this commentary, taking also all information from the case study summary report

(D3.5.) into account. At the moment, the report shows a solid understanding of the cocoa trading system, based on literature and interviews, but there is a need to verify all relevant different hypotheses.

Case Study #7

Impacts of EU policies on local dairy value chains in West Africa

Lead organization & name of lead contact: Oxfam-Solidarité, Fairouz Gazdallah & Marieke Kruis

Case Study Commentary

Introduction

The study aims to provide West African public authorities, farmers' and livestock farmers' organizations, civil society organizations and European players with information on the effects of imports and trade policies on developing the local dairy value chain in West Africa (including labour and food security issues). Also, it aims to assess how trade mechanisms are used in that context.

References to the different legal fields

The study is currently in its first phase – literature review and statistics analysis – and has not yet produced significant results. Nevertheless, the study points to engagement with significant trade regulations, such as the ECOWAS Common External Tariff, which showcases its focus on trade-related issues. The study, however, does not yet address questions concerning environmental protection, labour protection, or intellectual property, which may affect how agricultural trade works. Given the study's initial phase, we expect these issues to be covered in the final version of the case study report.

Assessment of the relevant legal provisions

The assessment of the relevant legal texts involved and directly related to issues addressed in the case study will be presented in the final version of this commentary, taking also all information from the case study summary report (D3.5.) into account.

Case Study #8

Belgian Consumption of Sugarcane Ethanol from Brazil and Peru. Shared responsibilities of human rights violations

Lead organization & name of lead contact: Oxfam Belgium, Alba Saray Pérez Terán

Case Study Commentary

Introduction

The study aims to assess the conditions under which Belgian biofuel consumption from Brazil and Peru are in light of the Clean Energy for All European Package and the Renewable Energy Directive. In doing so, it looks at various factors impacting trade and environment.

References to the different legal fields

The study is wide-ranging and addresses most of the legal fields set out above. It deals with human rights-related issues of various natures (including labour protection and illegal dispossession); it engages with how these issues affect (or may affect) trade between Latin-American countries and Belgium and raises many questions concerning the competitive nature of bioethanol given the way it is nowadays produced in both Brazil and Peru. The one area where it still lacks some reference is intellectual property. Nevertheless, in light of the current report stage, this seems to be something that can be easily added.

Assessment of the relevant legal provisions

The assessment of the relevant legal texts involved and directly related to issues addressed in the case study will be presented in the final version of this commentary, taking also all information from the case study summary report (D3.5.) into account.

Case Study #9

Human right due diligence in the coffee value chain

Lead organization & name of lead contact: Oxfam Wereldwinkels, Sarah Vaes

Contributions by [C-Lever](#)

Case Study Commentary

Introduction

This case study is centred around the coffee value chain that starts at a coffee cooperative in Southwestern Uganda and leads to a medium-sized mission-driven food retailer in Belgium. The study discusses questions raised in key regulatory instruments, such as the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGPs) and the upcoming EU Corporate Sustainable Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD).

[References to the different legal fields](#)

The study references the importance of various due diligence legislations enacted in Europe in the last decade. In light of such legislation, it looks at the conditions under which fair trade of Ugandan coffee occurs. While it focuses substantially on human rights issues, such as child labour and minimum wage, little is said about the regulatory framework conditioning import/export. The study mentions the little access Ugandan coffee has to certification schemes. While that touches upon questions of competition and contract, it does not extend to overall questions of international trade – apart from a brief mention in the table on page 13 concerning subsidies. However, the authors mention that the study must still be completed.

[Assessment of the relevant legal provisions](#)

The assessment of the relevant legal texts involved and directly related to issues addressed in the case study will be presented in the final version of this commentary, taking also all information from the case study summary report (D3.5.) into account.

Case Study #10

Beef and policy coherence for sustainable development

Lead organization & name of lead contact: Research Centre on Animal Production, Department of Economics and Engineering, Italy (C.R.P.A).

Authors: *Alberto Menghi, Lorena Giglio, Serena Soffiantini, Stefano Pignedoli, Assuntina Palamara*

Case Study Commentary

Introduction

This case study investigates the trade mechanism between nine countries in Africa (Morocco, Namibia, South Africa), America (Argentina, Brazil, United States of America) and Europe (France, Germany, Italy). It then looks at the various environmental impacts following such trade mechanisms.

References to the different legal fields

The study is comprehensive and addresses most of the legal fields set out above. More importantly, it looks at the environmental effects of the various trade mechanisms put in place. In this context, it also looks at the different social effects of these mechanisms. Notably, the focus is given to labour protection issues, including occupational health and safety (OHS) matters. While the report covers various trade-related issues, competition analysis could still strengthen it. This could provide an interesting leeway to understand how the various countries assess and use the trade mechanisms to their advantage.

Assessment of the relevant legal provisions

The assessment of the relevant legal texts involved and directly related to issues addressed in the case study will be presented in the final version of this commentary, taking also all information from the case study summary report (D3.5.) into account.

Case Study #11

Private standards and sustainable trade

Lead organization & name of lead contact: Research Centre on Animal Production, Department of Economics and Engineering, Italy.

Because of delays in ongoing fieldwork with GlobalG.A.P. (Avocado value chain in Kenya; Mango value chain in Kenya), no report was provided yet to take into account for assessment here.

Case Study #12

Ethical Trade Initiatives in the South African Wine Industry

Lead organization & name of lead contact: North-West University (NWU), TRADE Research Focus Area, South Africa. Ernst Idsardi

Case Study Commentary

Introduction

The present case study focuses on the Ethical Trade Initiatives in the South African Wine industry. It engages with various factors impacting the wine trade and assesses whether the new initiatives align with certain regulations, such as the Economic Partnership Agreement (EPA).

References to the different legal fields

The study maps out various trade measures (tariff and non-tariff) that condition the exporting of South African wine to Europe. In that respect, the study is quite comprehensive in analysing the existing trade regulatory mechanisms that affect such processes. It also delves into analysing how regulations affect local and international competition of South African wines. In this context, trade, competition, and contract laws are well covered. It would, however, be interesting to see more engagement with how environmental and labour regulations in the wine industry may affect the trade processes and the import/export relationship between South Africa and Europe.

Assessment of the relevant legal provisions

The assessment of the relevant legal texts involved and directly related to issues addressed in the case study will be presented in the final version of this commentary, taking also all information from the case study summary report (D3.5.) into account.

Case Study #13

Dairy production, standards and competitiveness in global markets

Lead organization & name of lead contact: Research Centre on Animal Production, Department of Economics and Engineering, Italy (C.R.P.A)

Authors: Alberto Menghi, Lorena Giglio, Serena Soffiantini, Stefano Pignedoli, Annunziata Palamara, Dorothee Boelling* Andrea Bassi**, Marco Guzzetti**

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Case Study Commentary

Introduction

The present case study examines the impact that labour conditions and costs have on the competitiveness of dairy products in international trade. It takes particular stock of the local rules and legislation, considering labour conditions are highly variable. For this case study, the following countries were analysed: Africa (Algeria, South Africa, Zimbabwe), America (Argentina, Brazil, United States of America) and Europe (France, Germany, Italy).

References to the different legal fields

The study is quite comprehensive in assessing the labour conditions in the different countries. While this allows us to understand more about the regulations concerned with labour protection and competitiveness, it does not lend much to grasping how trade flows operate. Although the report provides an excellent analysis of such trade processes, it would be important to understand how and whether they follow specific regulations. Also, there is not much concerning intellectual property in the report, which could be helpful. Lastly, it would also be important to understand better the local regulations concerning environmental protections – e.g., emissions control in farming – and animal welfare. Nevertheless, the authors indicate much yet to be included in the report. Therefore, we expect this information to be present in a later version.

Assessment of the relevant legal provisions

The assessment of the relevant legal texts involved and directly related to issues addressed in the case study will be presented in the final version of this commentary, taking also all information from the case study summary report (D3.5.) into account.

Case Study #14

Governing Trade to Influence Land-use and Food Systems Pathways: The Expansion of Soy-meat Complex in the MATOPIBA Brazilian Frontier

Lead Organization & name of lead contact: Technical University of Madrid. Team: Matheus Alvez Zanella, Maria Bustamante, Pablo Vidueira, Maddalena Bettoni, Cintya Manrique

Case Study Commentary

Introduction

The case study looks at soy production for soy-meat development in the MATOPIBA region in Brazil. It focuses on various trade issues, including developing specific food-system pathways and promoting sustainable land use. In doing so, the study also engages with topics related to the human rights of workers in the region.

References to the different legal fields

The study engages with various legal fields, including contract law (especially concerning certification schemes), land rights, and food law. The study also addresses how Free Trade Agreements (FTAs) could affect production in the MATOPIBA region. Yet, it would be interesting to see a better articulation of how environmental regulations may also affect trade-related activities of stakeholders based in the MATOPIBA region. Also, it is important to highlight how international regulations may be directing many of the actions taken in the many soy-meat complexes concerning human rights and trade. This is briefly mentioned when the study discusses the possibility of new, more stringent rules to regulate trade if an EU-Mercosur trade agreement were to be concluded. Nevertheless, the authors indicate that there is also much to be incorporated in the report in this respect, and we expect to see these other areas covered.

Assessment of the relevant legal provisions

The assessment of the relevant legal texts involved and directly related to issues addressed in the case study will be presented in the final version of this

commentary, taking also all information from the case study summary report (D3.5.) into account.

Case Study #15

Agricultural trade, food systems and ecological resilience in North Africa

Lead organization & name of lead contact: Transnational Institute (TNI); Pietje Vervest and Sylvia Kay

Commentary

Introduction

The case study initially focused mainly on examining the Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Agreement (DCFTA) between the EU and Tunisia. Because negotiations stalled, the study expanded its scope to develop a comparative case study on agricultural trade between the EU and North Africa, focusing on the olive oil value chain in Tunisia and the potato value chain in Egypt.

References to the different legal fields

While the study deals significantly with the different agri-food systems implemented in both Tunisia and Egypt, it still does not engage meaningfully with questions concerning the existing trade regulations and how they have impacted the systems' design. It does reference the various environmental and labour issues involved, but very little can be said about how the system defines the conditions for the import/export of products.

There is no information on questions concerning the intellectual property of seeds used in the farming process, and very few information on how small farms are marginalised vis-à-vis large firms in terms of access to inputs. This in turn affects their competitiveness, and hence, competition issues too merit attention.

The authors indicate that the study must yet be completed. Therefore, we expect many of these issues to be still covered.

Assessment of the relevant legal provisions

The assessment of the relevant legal texts involved and directly related to issues addressed in the case study will be presented in the final version of this

commentary, taking also all information from the case study summary report (D3.5.) into account.